

The Effect of Work Discipline, Work Environment and Transformational Leadership on Employee Productivity with Organizational Effectiveness as Mediating Variable in CV. Jaya Bangun Persada

Maulidia Andini Putri
 Master of Management Programme Student,
 Universitas Mercu Buana,
 Jakarta – Indonesia

Setyo Riyanto,
 Associates Professor,
 Universitas Mercu Buana,
 Jakarta – Indonesia

Abstract:- This study aims to analyze the influence of work discipline, work environment and transformational leadership with employee productivity and organizational effectiveness as a mediating variable at CV. Jaya Bangun Persada. The population of this study were all employees, with a total sample of 115 employees. The data analysis method uses the Structural Equation Model-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS). The results found that Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Employee Productivity. Work environment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Productivity. Transformational Leadership has no positive and insignificant effect on Employee Productivity. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Effectiveness. Work Environment has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Effectiveness. Transformational Leadership has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Effectiveness. Employee Productivity has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Effectiveness. Work Discipline has a positive and significant impact on Employee Productivity mediated by Organizational Effectiveness. Work Environment has a positive and

significant impact on Employee Productivity mediated by Organizational Effectiveness. Transformational Leadership on Employee Productivity has no positive and insignificant influence which is mediated by Organizational Effectiveness.

Keywords:- Work Discipline, Work Environment, Transformational Leadership, Employee Productivity, and Organizational Effectiveness.

I. INTRODUCTION

As a small construction company in the housing sector in the context of realizing skills and work productivity it will focus on development strategy that includes equity, growth, and stability. Then equity is not just expanding job opportunities but is more concern about business opportunities, distribution of income, and development alignment. The transition some of the workforce in the construction sector is not easy, including upgrading the skills of the workforce is crucial in this process. Therefore the demand for workforce skills is a strategic choice to increase productivity, especially in the construction sector.

Table 1: Labor Force Report Construction in Indonesia

Uraian Description	Satuan Units	2018	2019	2020	2021	Rata-rata Laju Pertumbuhan (%)
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
1. Jumlah Angkatan Kerja/ Number of Labor Force	orang	133 355 571	135 859 695	138 221 938	140 152 575	2,29
2. Jumlah Penduduk Bekerja Sektor Konstruksi/ Number of Construction Workers	orang	8 457 293	8 675 449	8 066 497	8 293 769	0,58
3. Tingkat Kesempatan Kerja Sektor Konstruksi/ Employment Rate of Construction	%	6,34	6,39	5,84	5,92	-1,68
4. PDB Sektor Konstruksi/ GDP of Construction	(miliar Rp)	1 562 297	1 701 741	1 652 660		
5. Elastisitas Tenaga Kerja Sektor Konstruksi/ Construction Labor Elasticity		-0,02	0,08	2,98		

Sumber/Source: Keadaan Angkatan Kerja di Indonesia Agustus 2021, BPS
 Labor Force Situation in Indonesia August 2021, BPS-Statistics Indonesia

Table 2: Index of Labor Productivity Figures in Various Industrial Sectors

Sektor	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24
A. Pertanian, Kehutanan, dan Perikanan	2.97	3.03	2.21
B. Pertambangan dan Penggalian	(1.28)	(1.47)	(2.54)
C. Industri Pengolahan	3.34	3.41	2.59
D. Pengadaan Listrik dan Gas	3.42	3.50	2.68
E. Pengadaan Air, Pengelolaan Sampah, Limbah dan Daur Ulang	4.13	4.21	3.38
F. Konstruksi	5.00	5.06	4.21
G. Perdagangan Besar dan Eceran; Reparasi Mobil dan Sepeda Motor	3.44	3.51	2.69
H. Transportasi dan Pergudangan	5.22	5.28	4.43
I. Penyediaan Akomodasi dan Makan Minum	4.08	4.15	3.33
J. Informasi dan Komunikasi	7.63	7.57	6.60
K. Jasa Keuangan dan Asuransi	5.76	5.80	4.93
L. Real Estate	4.09	4.17	3.34
M,N. Jasa Perusahaan	6.42	6.43	5.53
O. Administrasi Pemerintahan, Pertahanan dan Jaminan Sosial Wajib	2.59	2.65	1.82
P. Jasa Pendidikan	4.81	4.87	4.03
Q. Jasa Kesehatan dan Kegiatan Sosial	6.25	6.27	5.38
R,S,T,U. Jasa lainnya	6.33	6.35	5.45
PRODUK DOMESTIK BRUTO	3.85	3.92	3.10

Increased productivity is related to the time needed to complete the job and will directly affect the amount of costs required. Therefore CV. Jaya Bangun Persada has an interest in knowing the performance of workforce to increase

profitability. In these conditions, the biggest challenge in developing human resources is to teach unskilled workers is the main focus of the labor force in CV. Jaya Bangun Persada.

Table 3: Performance Report of the Ministry of PUPR (Directorate General of Housing)

Sasaran/Indikator	Tahun	Capaian
Kinerja		
Tingkat efektivitas dan efisiensi tata kelola penyelenggaraan perumahan	2019	88,69%
Tingkat efektivitas dan efisiensi tata kelola penyelenggaraan perumahan	2020	102,20%
Tingkat efektivitas dan efisiensi tata kelola penyelenggaraan perumahan	2021	103,75%

Every year the result of performance increasing effectiveness and efficiency of housing management is level up. The difference between CV. Jaya Bangun Persada when the process of infrastructure there are always problems during in the middle of working.

There is a lot of prospect data by employees of CV. Jaya Bangun Persada productivity and effectiveness is a concern of management to increase. To get an initial picture, a pre-survey was conducted on 115 employees so that it can be concluded that discipline, environment, and leadership are factors that play an important role in increasing agent productivity and effectiveness.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

- Employee productivity is a tool to measurement in organization are empowered to achive results and maximum of work performance by sacrifice the minimum possible resources (Setya, 2018).
- Organizational effectiveness is managing something accurately, objectively, and comprehensive according to organization goals. (Steers, 2015).
- Discipline is management action to enforce organization standards (Mangkunegara, 2017). Work Discipline is

developing strength in employees, then employees can adopt regulator decisions and high values of work and behavior. (Hamali, 2018).

- (Fitriani, K, 2021) argues that work environment is around workers who can influence themselves and capable to carrying on their duties. More specifically, Mangkunegara (2016) work environment can be divided into two categories, which is physical and non-physical work. The physical work is condition around the workplace that can affect employees either directly or indirectly. While non physical work is the conditions into relations with leader, colleague, and employees. (Rinaldi et al, 2018)
- (Mahmood, 2019) defines transformational leadership is a process which leader as arole models to encourage creativity, provide inspirational motivation, and involved to supporting also guide employees to achieved vision and goals organization. According to (Huang, Chen, and Chang, 2015), transformational leadership is a set of behavior that motivate employees to achieve performance beyond expectations by changing employee attitudes, beliefs, and values.

Based on the literature above, a research framework is prepared that shows the relationship between variables Monetary Transmision to Financial Market Theory

Fig. 1: Framework

- H1: Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Employee Productivity.
- H2: Work Environment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Productivity.
- H3: Transformational Leadership has a positive and significant effect on Employee Productivity
- H4: Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Effectiveness.
- H5: Work Environment has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Effectiveness.
- H6: Transformational Leadership has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Effectiveness.
- H7: Employee Productivity has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Effectiveness
- H8: Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Employee Productivity through Organizational Effectiveness.
- H9: Work Environment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Productivity through Organizational Effectiveness
- H10: Transformational Leadership has a positive and significant effect on Employee Productivity through Organizational Effectiveness

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Quantitative research was chosen because it processed the questionnaire data and converted it into numbers according to the respondents' answers. The population is 115 employees in CV. Jaya Bangun Persada. The total sample is an appropriate sampling technique. To answer the proposed hypothesis, SEM analysis with the PLS 3.0 program was used because of the mediating variables (intervening).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis testing results: The research variable hypothesis was answered through SEM-PLS analysis.

A. Testing of the measurement model's outer model

The measurement model's or outer model's test findings are used to gauge the validity and dependability of the model. The convergent and discriminant validity of the indicators as well as the composite reliability of the indicator block were used to evaluate the outer model with reflexive indicators. The outcomes of the AVE convergent test are displayed in the table below.

Table 4: Value for Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variabel	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Employee_Productivity	0,565
Organizational_Effectiveness	0,573
Transformational_Leadership	0,872
Work_Discipline	0,547
Work_Environment	0,647

Table 2 above demonstrates the PLS results, which indicate that all variables have an AVE value >0,5. Each

variable in the study isn thus valid or satifies convergent validity requirements.

Table 5: Results of the Composite Reliability Test and Cronbach's Alpha

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Keterangan
Employee_Productivity (Y1)	0,914	0,928	Reliable
Organizational_Effectiveness (Y2)	0,851	0,889	Reliable
Transformational_Leadership (X3)	0,979	0,982	Reliable
Work_Discipline (X1)	0,883	0,906	Reliable
Work_Environment (X2)	0,864	0,901	Reliable

All latent variable values have a Composite Reliability value of less than 0.7, according to Table 5's findings from the Composite Reliability test. All latent variable values have a Cronbach's Alpha test. The occupational employee productivity variable has the greatest composite reliability score (0,928) and organizational effectiveness has the lowest (0,889).

According to the test findings for Cronbach's Alpha, the variable measuring transformational leadership has the highest value at 0,979 and the variable measuring

organizational effectiveness has the lowest value at (0,889). The construct has strong reliability, or the questionnaire utilized as a research tool is consistent and dependable based on these findings. (Ghozali, 2016)

B. Evaluation of the Inner Model for Measurement

To analyze the structural model (inner model) or test the hypothesis in this study by analyzing the R2, Predictive Relevance (Q2), and Overall Structural Model Validation (GoF) values.

Table 6: Results of the R-Square Calculation (R2)

Variabel	R ²	R ² Adjusted
Employee_Productivity	0,652	0,639
Organizational_Effectiveness	0,440	0,425

It is evident from Table 6 above that the Employee Productivity(Y1) construct's R Square value (R2) is 0.652. These findings suggest that the exogenous variables Work Discipline (X1), Work Environment (X2), and Transformational Leadership (X3) may explain 65,2% of the endogenous variable Employee Productivity (Y1) while other exogenous variables can explain the remaining 35,8%. At the same time, exogenous variables such as work discipline (X1), work environment (X2), and Transformational Leadership (X3) can account for 44,0% of the construct of occupational organizational effectiveness (Y2) While other external factors can account for the remaining 17.

Goodness of Fit or GoF index is used to evaluate measurement models and structural models. Besides, it also provides a simple measure of the overall prediction of the model. The criterion for the GoF value is 0.10 indicating small GoF, 0.25 indicating medium GoF and 0.36 indicating large GoF (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). The GoF value in PLS must be searched manually with the following formula.

$$GoF = \sqrt{AVE \times R2}$$

$$AVERAGE\ AVE\ VALUE = (0,565 + 0,573 + 0,872 + 0,547 + 0,647) / 5 = 0,641$$

$$Average\ R2\ Value = (0,652 + 0,440) / 2 = 0,546$$

$$Gof = \sqrt{0,641 \times 0,546} = 0,350 = 0,592$$

The results of the calculation of the Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) show a value of 0.592. Based on these results, it can be concluded that the combined performance of the measurement model (outer model) and the structural model (inner model) as a whole is good because the Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) value is more than 0.36 (GoF large scale).

Table 7: Hypothesis Analysis

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Organizational Effectiveness->Employee Productivity	0,282	0,281	0,071	3,990	0,000
Transformational Leadership -> Employee Productivity	0,166	0,169	0,062	2,662	0,008
Transformational Leadership -> Organizational Effectiveness	-0,173	-0,171	0,074	2,331	0,020
Work Discipline->Employee Productivity	0,627	0,626	0,053	11,743	0,083
Work Discipline -> Organizational Effectiveness	0,545	0,546	0,074	7,405	0,000
Work Environment->Employee Productivity	0,137	0,140	0,069	1,981	0,048
Work Environment->Organizational Effectiveness	0,287	0,295	0,079	3,610	0,000
Transformational Leadership ->Organizational Effectiveness->Employee Productivity	-0,049	-0,048	0,025	1,983	0,048
Work Discipline->Organizational Effectiveness->Employee Productivity	0,153	0,153	0,043	3,566	0,000
Work Environment->Organizational Effectiveness->Employee Productivity	0,081	0,084	0,033	2,471	0,014

Based on the hypothesis test, it is known employees CV. Jaya Bangun Persada work discipline have increase, so employee productivity will increase significantly. The work environment activities of the employees CV. Jaya Bangun Persada increase, so employee productivity will increase significantly. Transformational leadership of the employees CV. Jaya Bangun Persada not increase, so employee productivity not increase and not significantly. Work discipline have increased, so organizational effectiveness will increase significantly. Work environment have increased, so organizational effectiveness will increase significantly. Transformational leadership have increased, so organizational effectiveness will increase significantly. Increased work discipline can support the effect of organizational effectiveness on the employee productivity of CV. Jaya Bangun Persada employees. Furthermore, work environment can reinforce the effect of organizational effectiveness on the employee productivity of CV. Jaya Bangun Persada. But, transformational leadership cannot support organizational effectiveness of the CV. Jaya Bangun Persada, so the employee productivity not increase.

Work discipline activities explain that the productivity employees change because each disciplinary carried out by the employee experience. Effect by discipline affects value of employee productivity. Correlation between obedience to the rules of conduct in company to level of ability and understand all the work showing employees was able to finish the job. A high correlation between adherence to behavioral rules in a company to the level of hearing and understanding ability of all the work accomplished indicates that employees are able to accomplish a job well. By adherence to behavioral rules in a company can manage the awareness an employee has so that activities carried out in the company can produce productive results.

Observing work environment means trying to create work environment that suits the employees' wants and needs. Since it is a home construction company, it is expected that work will be done in the open each day. In the sense that leaders also contribute to caring for the working environment by creating a supportive, safe, comfortable, and peaceful

work environment that gives workers and workers greater enthusiasm for work.

Segoro and pratiwi (2021) state that work environment is an influential rise toward entrepreneurship, indicating that companies are applying a culture of respect within each partner, superior, and subordinate to make themselves useful and profitable.

In the course of employment, fellow employees are often faced with problems of differing principles, willpower, needs, character, feelings, and so on. Then it would require the presence of a capable leader Therefore it would require the presence of a leader capable of driving others or subordinates to unite the differences between employees to achieve a common goal. But it will not affect the leadership style with workers' productivity getting higher, it will not shape employees being industrious and having a good work ethic.

Arsyad, siwi, and sumampouw (2020) also claim with the same study that transformational leadership has no effect on leadership. This means that the leadership transformational is not a real impact on leadership. In this case the high or low leadership requisite forms that the leadership leadership leadership leadership to the employees does not show significant change.

Ilesanmi (2018) at his research explain the Labour's adherence to company standards set out in terms of personal performance and behavior is the most important. It can also meet the standards of job performance and be discreet and safe at work. Good discipline reflects a person's sense of responsibility for the tasks assigned to him. To enhance discipline, regulations are indispensable ina company will be able to achieve maximum organizational effectiveness.

Every company is obliged to create a good work environment for its employees to be mere Each company is required to create a good working environment for its employees so that they can work optimally, by creating a positive atmosphere of work environment that will certainly affect the company's effectiveness.

The existence of a coordinated link between charisma in the sense that leaders are capable of making sure employees can complete the job with the level of strategies used in the execution of a work program that indicates a leader's role is as a facilitator where a leader is able to encourage and create consciousness to make changes. Things to do for the company by making decisions that lead to priorities that should be done at all jobs.

Employees are assets to the company, and therefore the company must support any employees' wishes in order to thrive. If the company is not careful, it will be difficult to keep up with its growth.

There is a correlation between self-development such as the level of hearing ability and understanding of all the work done in natural view such as the level of strategic alignment

used in the performance of a work program indicating that employees have the potential of self that must continue to be developed in order to improve their quality Part of building good hr is ensuring that employees' development also requires respect for hard work while in the company, if its performance is good then it should be considered to give you a promotion of a raise so as to increase employee productivity.

C. Hypothesis Testing Results

Testing the hypothesis in this study uses the t-value compared to the t-table. The hypothesis is accepted if the t-value is greater than the t-table, whereas if the t-value is less than the t-table then the hypothesis is rejected. The data seen is the result of the bootstrapping process, both the direct effect (path coefficient) and the indirect effect (specific indirect effect). The results of the hypothesis test are as follows.

Table 8: Hypothesis test

Hipotesis	Path	t-value	t-table	Decision
Hipotesis 1	Work_Discipline->Employee_Productivity	6,922	1,96	Accept
Hipotesis 2	Work_Environment->Employee_Productivity	7,405	1,96	Accept
Hipotesis 3	Transformational_Leadership->Employee_Productivity	0,846	1,96	Rejected
Hipotesis 4	Work_Discipline->Organizational_Effectiveness	3,990	1,96	Accept
Hipotesis 5	Work_Environment->Organizational Effectiveness	3,730	1,96	Accept
Hipotesis 6	Transformational_Leadership->Organizational Effectiveness	2,331	1,96	Accept
Hipotesis 7	Employee_Productivity->Organizational_Effectiveness	3,610	1,96	Accept
Hipotesis 8	Work_Discipline->Employee_Productivity->Organizational Effectiveness	3,566	1,96	Accept
Hipotesis 9	Work_Environment->Employee_Productivity->Organizational Effectiveness	2,471	1,96	Accept
Hipotesis 10	Transformational_Leadership->Employee_Productivity->Organizational Effectiveness	1,983	1,96	Rejected

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

A. Conclusion

- Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Employee Productivity.
- Work Environment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Productivity.
- Transformational Leadership has no effect on Employee Productivity
- Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Effectiveness.
- Work Environment has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Effectiveness.
- Transformational Leadership has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Effectiveness.
- Employee Productivity has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Effectiveness
- Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Employee Productivity through Organizational Effectiveness.
- Work Environment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Productivity through Organizational Effectiveness

- Transformational Leadership has no effect on Employee Productivity through Organizational Effectiveness

DATA AVAILABILITY

The entire data used in this study is fully accessible to readers, especially future researchers, as long as this is done for the sake of academic research and not for commercial purposes.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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